

An Empirical Response Law for Galaxy and Dwarf Dynamics

EUGEN MACKE¹

¹*Professor Emeritus, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany*

ABSTRACT

A compact empirical response framework is introduced to organize late-time weak-field dynamics across rotation-supported galaxies and pressure-supported dwarfs. The method is based on radius-local inversion of co-located tuples of enclosed baryonic mass, characteristic radius, and observed circular velocity, yielding an empirical response coefficient that can be compared across systems and dynamical regimes.

Within the rotation-supported calibration domain, the inferred coefficients populate a tight inverse-mass ridge over approximately five decades in enclosed baryonic mass, including an independent halo-scale galaxy–galaxy lensing and satellite-kinematics cross-check at ~ 200 kpc. The ridge exhibits finite but structured scatter rather than exact constancy. Extending the same tuple-plane diagnostic to pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at their half-light radius increases the dynamic range to more than eight decades in mass and reveals systematic regime-dependent deviations.

Unlike a universal single-valued radial acceleration relation, the primary empirical benchmark adopted here is the stability and structured scatter of the tuple-plane ridge across radii, tracers, and dynamical states. The formulation is explicitly empirical and agnostic with respect to microscopic interpretation and defines falsification criteria based on slope stability, normalization drift, radial coherence, and cross-channel consistency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flat rotation curves beyond stellar disks, the empirical regularities summarized by the radial acceleration relation (RAR), and persistent small-scale tensions in Λ CDM (e.g., Kroupa 2012) motivate careful, data-driven tests of weak-field dynamics on galaxy scales. The lack of a direct detection of a dark-matter (DM) particle, together with the sensitivity of small-scale predictions to baryonic modeling, selection effects, and non-equilibrium dynamics, further motivates phenomenological descriptions that are compact and falsifiable.

A key empirical fact is that departures from purely baryonic Newtonian expectations tend to appear around accelerations of order $a_0 \sim 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$ (McGaugh et al. 2016), echoing the phenomenology captured by modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND) (Milgrom 1983). Recent results also indicate that the RAR is not a universal single-valued mapping across all dynamical states. Weak-lensing reconstructions extend the RAR into the low-acceleration halo regime by ~ 2.5 dex beyond the direct reach of rotation curves, anchoring the relation

with an independent mass channel (Mistele et al. 2024). In contrast, very low-mass, pressure-supported dwarfs show large scatter and even multi-valued loci in the resolved (g_N, g_{obs}) plane, indicating that g_N alone is insufficient to predict g_{obs} in that regime (Júlio et al. 2025).

An empirical response law for galaxy dynamics is introduced and calibrated. Writing the observed radial acceleration as $g_{\text{obs}} = v^2/r$, and the baryonic Newtonian acceleration as $g_N = GM(<r)/r^2$ (with $M(<r)$ the enclosed baryonic mass), the dynamical support is expressed as the response-level identity

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) = \frac{g_N(r)}{1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}, \quad (1)$$

where β_{eff} is a dimensionless response fraction that can be interpreted as the local fraction of additional (mass-equivalent) dynamical support beyond baryons. For rotation-supported disks, the data are well described by a one-parameter law in terms of a galaxy-wide coefficient G_{rot} ,

$$v^2(r) = \frac{GM(<r)}{r} \frac{1}{1 - M(<r)G_{\text{rot}}/(4\pi^2)}, \quad (2)$$

with a tight inverse mass scaling $G_{\text{rot}} = K_{\text{rot}}/M_{\text{ref}}$ in the calibration domain (Table 1, Table 2, Table 3, and

Fig. 5). This provides a compact, testable compression of rotation-curve phenomenology without selecting a unique microphysical interpretation (e.g. DM halo response, modified dynamics, or hybrid scenarios).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 defines the response notation and the G_{rot} law. Section 3 presents the calibration based on tuples and the mass scaling. Section 4 assembles observational and numerical evidence across disks, pressure-supported dwarfs. The final sections summarize falsifiable targets that distinguish a universal one-parameter mapping from explicit state conditioning tests.

2. WEAK-FIELD NOTATION AND THE EMPIRICAL G_{ROT} RESPONSE LAW

This section defines the weak-field quantities used throughout the paper and formulates the empirical response law calibrated in Table 1–Table 3. The presentation is intentionally phenomenological: the goal is a compact and testable organization of galaxy and dwarf dynamics. No claim is made that the additional dynamical support is the GR Lense–Thirring frame-dragging contribution. The gravito-electromagnetic (GEM) decomposition is used as a convenient weak-field language that separates scalar (Newtonian) and vector-like sectors, without committing to a unique microphysical completion.

Throughout, $M(< r)$ denotes the enclosed *baryonic* mass used in the kinematic analysis, and

$$g_N(r) = \frac{GM(< r)}{r^2} \quad (3)$$

is the corresponding Newtonian baryonic acceleration. The observed radial acceleration is

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) \equiv \frac{v^2(r)}{r}. \quad (4)$$

2.1. Empirical response fraction and state dependence

Response identity—The galaxy-scale phenomenology is organized through a response-level identity,

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) = \frac{g_N(r)}{1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}, \quad (5)$$

where the empirical response fraction is

$$\beta_{\text{eff}}(r) \equiv 1 - \frac{g_N(r)}{g_{\text{obs}}(r)} = 1 - \frac{GM(< r)}{r v^2(r)}. \quad (6)$$

Equivalently,

$$M_{\text{dyn}}(< r) = \frac{M(< r)}{1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}, \quad \frac{M_{\text{extra}}}{M_{\text{dyn}}} = \beta_{\text{eff}}(r), \quad (7)$$

so that β_{eff} can be interpreted as the local fraction of extra dynamical support (mass-equivalent) beyond baryons.

2.2. The G_{rot} rotation law (disk calibration domain) and its extension

Definition of G_{rot} and the generalized one-parameter law—Introduce the rotation frequency $\nu \equiv v/(2\pi r)$ as a notational device and define

$$a_{\text{rot}}(r) = \nu^2(r) r M(< r) G_{\text{rot}}, \quad [G_{\text{rot}}] = \text{kg}^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

This implies

$$\beta_{\text{eff}}(r) = \frac{M(< r) G_{\text{rot}}}{4\pi^2} \quad (9)$$

and hence the generalized G_{rot} rotation law

$$v^2(r) = \frac{GM(< r)}{r} \frac{1}{1 - M(< r) G_{\text{rot}} / (4\pi^2)} \quad (10)$$

$$G_{\text{rot}}(r) = \frac{4\pi^2}{M(< r)} \left(1 - \frac{g_N(r)}{g_{\text{obs}}(r)} \right) = \frac{4\pi^2 \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}{M(< r)}. \quad (11)$$

If Eq. (10) holds with a galaxy-wide radius-independent G_{rot} , then $G_{\text{rot}}(r)$ inferred from any radius r via Eq. (11) should be consistent within uncertainties. This makes the choice of evaluation radius explicit: different studies may report $(M(< r), r, v)$ at different characteristic radii (outer-disk tuples, halo-scale $r = 200$ kpc bins or dwarf half-light radii), but they map into the same tuple plane provided the inferred G_{rot} is radius-coherent for each system.

Consistency bound.—A finite, positive rotation speed requires

$$1 - \frac{M(< r) G_{\text{rot}}}{4\pi^2} > 0 \quad \forall r. \quad (12)$$

No implied upper mass bound.—The consistency condition $1 - M(< r) G_{\text{rot}} / (4\pi^2) > 0$ does not imply an upper limit on the mass of the galaxy. Under empirical scaling $G_{\text{rot}} = K_{\text{rot}} / M_{\text{ref}}$, the product $M G_{\text{rot}}$ follows a narrow, but not strictly constant, distribution throughout the calibration domain of the disk. The bound therefore constrains the normalization K_{rot} rather than the absolute baryonic mass of galaxies.

3. EMPIRICAL CALIBRATION, MASS SCALING

3.1. Dataset and determination of G_{rot}

For each galaxy, one or more co-located tuples $(M(< r_i), r_i, v(r_i))$ are used, preferentially in the outer disk (often near the flat part), but not restricted to this region, to calculate $G_{\text{rot}}(r_i)$ from Eq. (11) (or equivalently $\beta_{\text{eff}} = M(< r) G_{\text{rot}} / (4\pi^2)$).

Reason for the outer-disk preference. Tuples are preferentially selected in the outer disk/near the flat part because this is typically the radial regime where the

148 kinematic measurement is most stable and where the en-
 149 closed baryonic mass estimate is least model-dependent
 150 in the available literature products (e.g. reduced sensi-
 151 tivity to bulge–disk decomposition and inner-bar sys-
 152 tematics). Fully resolved baryonic mass profiles $M(< r)$
 153 with well-characterized uncertainties are rarely pub-
 154 lished for large, heterogeneous samples; the tuple-based
 155 approach therefore relies on the most robust co-located
 156 mass estimates reported at the measurement radius,
 157 while remaining applicable to other radii when such es-
 158 timates are available.

159 *Operational advantage of the co-located tuple approach.*—
 160 The tuple-based calibration does not require a fully re-
 161 solved baryonic mass profile $M(< r)$ for each galaxy.
 162 Instead, it only requires an enclosed baryonic mass esti-
 163 mate at the specific kinematic radius where $v(r)$ is mea-
 164 sured, i.e. a co-located tuple $(M(< r_i), r_i, v(r_i))$.

165 This construction makes the framework directly ap-
 166 plicable to heterogeneous literature data products and
 167 to summary measurements evaluated at very different
 168 radii, including outer-disk rotation-curve points, fidu-
 169 cial radii such as $r_{1/2}$ for pressure-supported dwarfs,
 170 and halo-scale (~ 200 kpc) values inferred from galaxy–
 171 galaxy lensing and satellite kinematics. In all cases, the
 172 empirical test is performed in the same tuple plane by
 173 inverting Eq. (10) at the measurement radius.

174 If several tuples are available, a galaxy–level estimate
 175 is the weighted inverse-variance mean of $G_{\text{rot}}(r_i)$. When
 176 sources provide uncertainties per-object, they are used;
 177 otherwise, errors are estimated as described in the next
 178 paragraph.

179 The empirical test is therefore not tied to the exist-
 180 ence of high-precision global $M(< r)$ profiles, but to
 181 the internal consistency of the inferred response coef-
 182 ficient G_{rot} across independently measured co-located
 183 tuples.

184 *Uncertainty propagation and quality control.*—Table 2
 185 does not report errors per quoted object. Uncertain-
 186 ties are therefore estimated as follows: (i) when two
 187 or more co-located tuples exist for a given galaxy,
 188 the tuple–to–tuple scatter of $G_{\text{rot}}(r_i)$ provides the em-
 189 pirical $\sigma_{G_{\text{rot}}}$; (ii) otherwise, conservative default frac-
 190 tional errors are adopted and propagated by Monte
 191 Carlo ($N = 10^4$ draws per tuple): $\delta M/M = 0.30$,
 192 $\delta v/v = 0.05$, $\delta r/r = 0.10$. Each draw is filtered by
 193 (a) pole avoidance $M G_{\text{rot}}/(4\pi^2) < 1$ and (b) $G_{\text{rot}} > 0$.
 194 Tuple-level means and standard deviations define the
 195 weights for galaxy–level averaging and for the regres-
 196 sions in Sect. 3.2. As a robustness check, an unweighted
 197 fixed-slope (–1) log–log regression produces an inter-
 198 cept consistent with Eq. (14) within the 95% CI.

199 *Internal radial coherence.*—Within a given galaxy, G_{rot}
 200 is expected to be radius-independent. Coherence is as-
 201 sessed from the scatter of $G_{\text{rot}}(r_i)$ about the inverse-
 202 variance weighted galaxy mean and compared to the
 203 propagated uncertainty band, for each galaxy with mul-
 204 tiple tuples.

205 3.2. Global mass scaling: tuple-based regression

206 The tuple-based inversion implies an inverse mass scal-
 207 ing

$$208 \quad G_{\text{rot}} \propto M_{\text{ref}}^{-1}; \quad M_{\text{ref}} \equiv M(< r_{\text{ref}}) \text{ of the calibration tuple.} \quad (13)$$

209 Here r_{ref} denotes the measurement radius of the cal-
 210 ibration tuple. Depending on the data set, it may
 211 correspond to an outer-disk rotation-curve point, to
 212 $r_{\text{ref}} = 200$ kpc for the DECaLS bins, or to $r_{\text{ref}} = r_{1/2}$
 213 for pressure-supported dwarfs.

214 For the present sample (Appendix A), the data are
 215 well described by the fixed-slope line

$$216 \quad G_{\text{rot}} = \frac{K_{\text{rot}}}{M_{\text{ref}}}, \quad K_{\text{rot}} = 32.2 \pm 4.2 \quad (1\sigma). \quad (14)$$

217 For transparency, the ridge dispersion is quantified in
 218 log-space by the residual

$$219 \quad \Delta_{\text{ridge}} \equiv \log_{10} \left(\frac{M_{\text{ref}} G_{\text{rot}}}{K_{\text{rot}}} \right) = \log_{10} G_{\text{rot}} - \log_{10} \left(\frac{K_{\text{rot}}}{M_{\text{ref}}} \right). \quad (15)$$

220 For the disk tuples in Table 2, $\text{rms}(\Delta_{\text{ridge}}) = 0.059$ dex
 221 (median = 0.008 dex), corresponding to a $\simeq 13\%$ frac-
 222 tional scatter in $M_{\text{ref}} G_{\text{rot}}$ about the ridge. For the DE-
 223 CaLS halo-scale bins (Table 1), $\text{rms}(\Delta_{\text{ridge}}) = 0.072$ dex
 224 (median = 0.071 dex). Combining the disk tuples with
 225 the DECaLS bins gives $\text{rms}(\Delta_{\text{ridge}}) = 0.063$ dex, and in-
 226 cluding the pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at $r_{1/2}$
 227 (Table 3) yields $\text{rms}(\Delta_{\text{ridge}}) = 0.065$ dex across all chan-
 228 nels. The complete disk compilation spans $M_{\text{ref}} G_{\text{rot}} \simeq$
 229 22–39 (Table 2).

230 *External check with DECaLS GGL and satellite kinematics*
 231 *(Ma–Zhang–Wang).*—DECaLS DR8 weak lensing was
 232 applied to two samples of SDSS central galaxies: a *total*
 233 sample of 304,162 centrals (quiescent and star-forming)
 234 and a *star-forming* sample of 129,278 centrals (Ma et al.
 235 2025; Dey et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2022). Each sample is
 236 divided into six stellar-mass bins ($\Delta \log M_* = 0.5$ dex).
 237 Ma et al. (2025) define the baryonic masses in Table
 238 1 with the bin-averaged stellar masses (column 3) and
 239 the GGL-modeled gas masses (column 4); see also Com-
 240 parat et al. (2022); Bregman et al. (2018); Bogdán &
 241 Vogelsberger (2022); Nicastro et al. (2023). Using the
 242 rotation speeds provided at $r = 200$ kpc and inserting

Table 1. Halo-scale bin-averaged values at $r \simeq 200$ kpc.

ID	$G_{\text{rot}} \text{ (kg}^{-1}\text{)}$	$M_{\text{ref}} \text{ (kg)}$
SF 1	4.20×10^{-39}	9.30×10^{39}
SF 2	1.29×10^{-39}	2.99×10^{40}
SF 3	1.01×10^{-39}	3.81×10^{40}
SF 4	2.75×10^{-40}	1.37×10^{41}
SF 5	1.31×10^{-40}	2.83×10^{41}
SF 6	2.82×10^{-41}	1.21×10^{42}
Total 1	2.36×10^{-39}	1.65×10^{40}
Total 2	8.11×10^{-40}	4.75×10^{40}
Total 3	5.87×10^{-40}	6.51×10^{40}
Total 4	1.47×10^{-40}	2.52×10^{41}
Total 5	4.39×10^{-41}	8.05×10^{41}
Total 6	2.80×10^{-42}	9.07×10^{42}

NOTE—Values are from [Ma et al. \(2025\)](#); G_{rot} is inferred by inverting Eq. (10) with $M_{\text{ref}} \equiv M(< r_{\text{ref}})$ and $r_{\text{ref}} = 200$ kpc.

Figure 1. Tuple-plane calibration of the empirical response coefficient. For each co-located tuple ($M(< r_{\text{ref}})$, r_{ref} , $v(r_{\text{ref}})$), Eq. (10) is inverted to infer G_{rot} at the measurement radius, with $M_{\text{ref}} \equiv M(< r_{\text{ref}})$. Blue circles: disk calibration tuples. Red triangles: external DECaLS bin-wise points at $r \simeq 200$ kpc. The solid line shows the fixed-slope inverse-mass ridge $G_{\text{rot}} = K_{\text{rot}}/M_{\text{ref}}$ with $K_{\text{rot}} = 32.2$. Across the $\simeq 5$ dex mass range spanned by the disk+DECaLS channel, no systematic deviation from the ridge or change in normalization is observed.

Eq. (10) yields bin-wise factors G_{rot} . The twelve resulting mean values (IDs *SF1–SF6* and *Total1–Total6*) are listed in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 1 (filled triangles). All points lie on the empirical M^{-1} ridge with the uncertainty band quoted, without retuning of parameters. *Mass-scale coverage.* With M in SI units, the empirical scaling $G_{\text{rot}}(M) = K_{\text{rot}}/M$ with $K_{\text{rot}} = 32.2$ is maintained throughout the enclosed baryonic-mass interval $M \simeq (1.0 \times 10^{38} - 9.0 \times 10^{42})$ kg ($5.1 \times 10^7 - 4.5 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$). The disk-calibration tuples together with the DECaLS lensing/satellite-kinematics bins therefore span $\simeq 5$ dex in enclosed baryonic mass within the rotation-supported disk+halo channel, with Fig. 1 showing no systematic deviation from the inverse-mass ridge and no evidence for a change in normalization across that range. When pressure-supported dwarfs, evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ (Table 3), are mapped into the same tuple-plane diagnostic, the combined dynamic range extends to more than eight decades in $M(< r)$ (Fig. 5).

Within the one-parameter law of Eq. (10), rotation-supported galaxies and gas-rich dwarfs in the present sample are described using their enclosed baryonic mass $M(< r)$ at the measurement radius and the mass-dependent response coefficient $G_{\text{rot}}(M)$. Pressure-supported dwarfs are evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ within the same tuple formalism (Table 3). No additional phenomenological dark-matter halo component is introduced at the level of the kinematic fits.

4. OBSERVATIONAL AND NUMERICAL EVIDENCE

This section summarizes the observational evidence relevant to the empirical response law introduced in Sect. 2 and calibrated in Sect. 3.

4.1. Galaxies and rotation-supported (gas-rich) dwarfs

Milky Way and M31 fits.—Equation (10) is applied to two benchmark spirals, the Milky Way (MW) and Andromeda (M31). In the interpretation of Sect. 2.2 and 3, the parameter G_{rot} serves as an empirical response coefficient for rotation-supported disks. The fits assume an axisymmetric disk supported by rotation modeled as concentric circular rings. The baryonic masses $M(< r)$, the rotation speeds $v(r)$, and the radii r are compiled from Refs. [Sofue \(2015, 2016\)](#); [Bland-Hawthorn & Gerhard \(2016\)](#). Deviations from axial symmetry, detailed feedback features, and the halo substructure are neglected at this level. Representative quantities of tuples are listed in Appendix A. For the Milky Way, $G_{\text{rot}} = 2.20 \times 10^{-40} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ reproduces the adopted rotation curve; for M31, $G_{\text{rot}} = 1.25 \times 10^{-40} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ provides the corresponding fit. A representative reconstruction for MW is shown in Fig. 2.

The total baryonic masses are $M_{\text{bar}} \simeq 7.5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (MW) and $M_{\text{bar}} \simeq 1.3 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ (M31; $r \leq 36$ kpc), consistent with the cited literature. At the same radii, Newtonian dynamical estimates yield $M_{\text{dyn}} \simeq 4.5 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ (MW) and $M_{\text{dyn}} \simeq 7.9 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ (M31), i.e., $M_{\text{dyn}}/M_{\text{tot}} \simeq 5.8$ for both galaxies. The dynamical mass

Figure 2. Milky Way benchmark fit using the one-parameter response law (Eq. (10)) with a galaxy-wide constant G_{rot} . The solid red curve shows the used circular-speed profile $v(r)$, the associated enclosed baryonic mass profile $M(< r)$ (solid black curve) and the Newtonian dynamical mass M_{dyn} (solid blue curve) at each radius (not a requirement for a fully resolved mass model for all galaxies). The inferred total baryonic and dynamical masses are consistent with literature expectations, providing a sanity check that the fitted response reproduces a plausible mass and velocity distribution over the measured radial range.

for $r \leq 200$ kpc of Milky Way ($M_{\text{dyn}} \simeq 6.4 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$) is consistent with $M_{\text{vir}} = 7.32^{+1.98}_{-1.53} \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ (Ou et al. 2025). Despite this apparent mass discrepancy, the outer HI radii and circular velocities place the Milky Way and M31 on the tight HI radius–velocity relation (Meurer et al. 2018). Within the present framework, this is consistent with the empirical mass scaling: $G_{\text{rot}} \propto M_{\text{ref}}^{-1}$ (Sec. 3.2) in the rotation-supported regime.

Acceleration analysis.—Figure 3 summarizes the decomposition of the observed acceleration $g_{\text{obs}} \equiv v^2/r$ into the baryonic Newtonian part g_N and the empirical additional support a_{rot} ,

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) = g_N(r) + a_{\text{rot}}(r), \quad g_N(r) = \frac{GM(< r)}{r^2}. \quad (16)$$

At small radii ($r \lesssim 6$ kpc) the Newtonian term dominates. At intermediate radii ($r \simeq 8$ –12 kpc) the two contributions are comparable. In the outer disk ($r \gtrsim 10$ kpc) the additional support compensates for the decline of g_N and maintains an approximately constant $g_{\text{obs}} \simeq (1.0 - 1.4) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$ over $\sim 6 - 20$ kpc.

At larger halo radii ($\gtrsim 50$ –100 kpc) both galaxies show a gradual decline of g_{obs} below a_0 as g_N becomes small. At large radii g_N and g_{obs} can differ by about an order of magnitude; for the Milky Way at $r \approx 90$ kpc, one has $g_{\text{obs}} \approx 1.1 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m s}^{-2}$ while $g_N \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m s}^{-2}$. This behavior is compatible with Eq. (5) because $\beta_{\text{eff}}(r)$ can saturate while $g_N(r)$ continues to fall, so that g_{obs}/g_N grows without driving the system toward the pole of Eq. (10).

Figure 3. Acceleration profiles for the Milky Way and M31 benchmark under the one-parameter response law (Eq. (10)). The empirical additional support is $a_{\text{rot}} = g_{\text{obs}}(r) - g_N(r)$, with $g_{\text{obs}}(r) = v^2(r)/r$ and $g_N(r) = GM_{\text{bar}}(< r)/r^2$ evaluated from the adopted enclosed baryonic mass at the same radii.

RAR representation (rotation-supported sample).—For the first twelve galaxies listed in Appendix A, the observed acceleration is computed from the measured rotation curves as $g_{\text{obs}}(r) = v_{\text{obs}}(r)^2/r$, and the Newtonian (baryonic) acceleration from the baryonic profiles as $g_N(r) = GM(< r)/r^2$. As a reference, the radial acceleration relation (RAR) (McGaugh et al. 2016) is

$$g_{\text{obs}} = \frac{g_N}{1 - \exp[-\sqrt{g_N/a_0}]}, \quad a_0 \simeq 1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}. \quad (17)$$

The empirical response identity of Eq. (5) provides the corresponding representation

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) = \frac{g_N(r)}{1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}, \quad (18)$$

with $\beta_{\text{eff}}(r) = M(< r)G_{\text{rot}}/(4\pi^2)$ in the disk calibration domain (Sect. 3).

Fig. 4 shows the correlation between g_{obs} and g_N for the sample, together with the McGaugh et al. curve (red dashed); the scatter is small and comparable to SPARC.

An illustrative mapping $\beta_{\text{eff}}(g_N)$ reproduces Eq. (17) for rotation-supported disks. This mapping is not used to redefine the fitted galaxy-wide parameter G_{rot} .

Interpretation. Fig. 4 is included as a consistency check in the rotation-supported regime. However, the primary empirical benchmark of the present work is the tuple-plane inverse-mass ridge, characterized by finite but structured scatter (Figure 1, Figure 5): the RAR is a projection of the same kinematic information, whereas the tuple plane inference directly tests the radius-local response across tracers and radii.

Figure 4. Radial-acceleration relation (RAR) consistency check for the rotation-supported calibration sample. The (g_N, g_{obs}) projection is constructed from the adopted co-located tuples used in the G_{rot} inference, and the points follow the standard McGaugh RAR within the quoted scatter. This panel serves as a sanity check; the primary empirical benchmark of this work is the tight inverse-mass ridge (with finite scatter) in the tuple plane (Figs. 1 and 5), which is radius-local and tracer-agnostic.

357 *Summary (rotation-supported regime).*—The MW and
 358 M31 fits, the disk tuple sample (Table 2), and the external
 359 DECaLS cross-check show that a single mass-scaled
 360 response coefficient $G_{\text{rot}}(M)$ suffices to describe the
 361 empirical dynamical support in the analyzed rotation-
 362 supported galaxies and gas-rich dwarfs. The empirical
 363 representation does not select a unique microphysical
 364 interpretation; it can be read as an effective mass map-
 365 ping, a modified-dynamics ν -law, or a compact summary
 366 of baryon–potential coupling.

367 4.2. Ultra-diffuse/low-surface-brightness galaxies and 368 the low-mass dwarf regime

369 *Rotation-supported LSB and gas-rich dwarfs (calibration
 370 domain).*—The calibration domain G_{rot} includes many
 371 low-surface-brightness (LSB) and gas-rich dwarf irreg-
 372 ulars (e.g. DDO-type systems) that remain predomi-
 373 nantly rotation-supported in H I.

374 *Pressure-supported, very low-mass dwarfs: non-universality
 375 and multi-valued loci (Júlio et al.).*—Júlio et al. (2025)
 376 study the radially resolved RAR of 12 nearby dwarfs
 377 with baryonic masses $10^4 < M_{\text{bar}}/M_{\odot} < 10^{7.5}$ us-
 378 ing stellar line-of-sight velocities and GravSphere Jeans
 379 modeling. Most dwarfs lie systematically above the
 380 low-mass extrapolation of the galactic RAR; individual
 381 galaxies trace multi-valued loci in (g_N, g_{obs}) and show
 382 substantial galaxy-to-galaxy scatter, leading to the con-
 383 clusion that g_N alone does not contain enough informa-
 384 tion to predict g_{obs} in this regime. EDGE simulations

385 in Λ CDM behave similarly, and observed deviations are
 386 not explained by strong tides in the sample.

387 *Mapping pressure-supported dwarfs into the tuple plane.*—
 388 Table 3 evaluates Eq. (10) for the dwarf sample at the
 389 (projected) half-light radius $r_{1/2}$. For each dwarf, G_{rot}
 390 is computed at $r_{1/2}$ via Eq. (11) using the enclosed
 391 baryonic mass $M_{\text{bar}}(< r_{1/2})$ and the dynamical accel-
 392 eration $g_{\text{obs}}(r_{1/2})$ reported by Júlio et al. (2025). This
 393 maps pressure-supported dwarfs to the same (M, G_{rot})
 394 tuple plane as the rotation-supported disk calibration
 395 tuples (Table 2) and the DECaLS halo-scale bins at
 396 $r = 200$ kpc (Table 1). Figure 5 overlays the three
 397 channels and shows that the three channels are broadly
 398 consistent with the M^{-1} ridge within the quoted scat-
 399 ter, although they are evaluated at different character-
 400 istic radii. Because Eq. (10) depends explicitly on r
 401 through $M(< r)$ and $g_{\text{obs}} = v^2/r$, its projection into
 402 the (g_N, g_{obs}) plane need not be single-valued, consis-
 403 tent with the multi-valued loci seen in the resolved dwarf
 404 RAR.

405 *Weak-lensing extension of the RAR at very low accelera-
 406 tions (Mistele et al.).*—Weak gravitational lensing pro-
 407 vides an independent constraint on the low-acceleration
 408 regime. Mistele et al. (2024) combine kinematic and
 409 weak-lensing data to construct the RAR over a large
 410 dynamic range, introducing a deprojection formula that
 411 converts excess surface densities to radial accelerations
 412 and finding that the weak-lensing RAR smoothly con-
 413 tinues the kinematic RAR by ~ 2.5 dex toward smaller
 414 accelerations. The result supports treating the galaxy-
 415 scale response law as compatible with lensing-based ac-
 416 celerations on $\gtrsim 100$ –300 kpc scales.

417 *Ultra-diffuse galaxies (UDGs).*—UDGs and related low-
 418 surface brightness systems span a wide range of inter-
 419 nal dynamical states (rotating and non-rotating classes)
 420 and therefore motivate conditioning dynamical compar-
 421 isons on kinematic state variables rather than enforcing
 422 a single universal mapping from g_N to g_{obs} across all
 423 low-surface-density systems.

424 4.3. Disk mergers, fast/slow rotators, and conditional 425 response tests

426 Integral-field surveys (e.g. SAURON and ATLAS^{3D})
 427 establish a kinematic dichotomy among early-type
 428 galaxies: most systems are fast rotators with significant
 429 specific angular momentum, while a minority of mas-
 430 sive, round systems are slow rotators with low λ_R and
 431 complex velocity fields (Cappellari et al. 2007; Emsellem
 432 et al. 2011; Krajnović et al. 2020).

433 Hydrodynamic simulations of disk mergers reproduce
 434 this dichotomy: co-rotating or mildly inclined encoun-

Figure 5. Tuple-plane mass scaling in the $G_{\text{rot}}-M$ diagnostic. Blue circles: rotation-supported disk calibration tuples (Table 2), with $M \equiv M_{\text{ref}} = M(< r_{\text{ref}})$. Red triangles: external DECaLS bin-wise values at $r \simeq 200$ kpc (Table 1), evaluated with the same tuple inversion. Purple triangles: pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ (Table 3). The solid line shows the fixed-slope inverse-mass ridge $G_{\text{rot}} = K_{\text{rot}}/M$ with $K_{\text{rot}} = 32.2$. Including pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ extends the tuple-plane mass coverage from the $\simeq 5$ dex disk+DECaLS channel to more than eight decades in $M(< r)$.

435 ters and sequences of minor mergers tend to yield fast-
 436 rotating remnants, whereas gas-poor major mergers
 437 with misaligned or counter-rotating progenitors, or mul-
 438 tiple dry mergers, generate slowly rotating, round sys-
 439 tems (Naab et al. 2006; Bois et al. 2011; Moody et al.
 440 2014). Observed examples with tidal debris and shells
 441 illustrate that fast and slow rotators can be interpreted
 442 as merger remnants with different orbital geometries and
 443 spin configurations (Duc et al. 2011).

444 Independent dynamical and lensing analyses indicate
 445 that both fast and slow rotators inhabit extended dark-
 446 matter halos, with increasing dark-matter fractions at
 447 several effective radii (Cappellari 2008; Koopmans et al.
 448 2009; Sonnenfeld et al. 2022). In this framework, the
 449 fast/slow-rotator dichotomy serves as a conditional test
 450 of state dependence: if additional support is conditioned
 451 on rotational coherence, fast rotators should lie closer
 452 to the rotation-supported regime, while slow rotators
 453 should show reduced activation. Conversely, any hot-
 454 support channel must remain constrained so as not to
 455 overpredict high-acceleration, dispersion-supported sys-
 456 tems. Conditional comparisons split by λ_R , interaction
 457 history, or kinematic regularity provide direct tests of
 458 cross-state consistency of the disk-calibrated response.

5. DISCUSSION

460 The present analysis introduces a radius-local empiri-
 461 cal response diagnostic for late-time weak-field dynam-
 462 ics and organizes heterogeneous kinematic information

463 through the inferred coefficient G_{rot} . The purpose of this
 464 section is (i) to summarize the empirical content of the
 465 tuple-plane ridge, (ii) to clarify the precise mathematical
 466 relation to the RAR/MOND-style representations, (iii)
 467 to delineate the open interpretation space without com-
 468 mitting to a microscopic mechanism, and (iv) to state
 469 quantitative falsification criteria.

5.1. What is established empirically

470
 471 *Rotation-supported systems (disk calibration domain).*—
 472 For disks and gas-rich, rotation-supported dwarfs, co-
 473 located tuples ($M(< r), r, v(r)$) define the Newtonian
 474 baryonic acceleration $g_N(r) = GM(< r)/r^2$ and the
 475 observed acceleration $g_{\text{obs}}(r) = v^2(r)/r$, and hence the
 476 empirical response fraction $\beta_{\text{eff}}(r) = 1 - g_N(r)/g_{\text{obs}}(r)$.
 477 Within the calibration domain (Sect. 3), the inferred
 478 values of G_{rot} populate a tight inverse-mass ridge in the
 479 (M, G_{rot}) tuple plane,

$$480 \quad G_{\text{rot}} \propto M_{\text{ref}}^{-1}, \quad M_{\text{ref}} \equiv M(< r_{\text{ref}}), \quad (19)$$

481 with fixed-slope normalization given in Eq. (14). This
 482 ridge persists across the mass range tested in Fig. 1 and
 483 is supported by an external halo-scale check from DE-
 484 CaLS galaxy-galaxy lensing and satellite kinematics at
 485 $r \simeq 200$ kpc (Sect. 3.2).

486 *What the ridge encodes.*—The tuple inversion implies

$$487 \quad M_{\text{ref}} G_{\text{rot}} = 4\pi^2 \beta_{\text{eff}}(r_{\text{ref}}), \quad (20)$$

488 so that the inverse-mass ridge corresponds to a *narrow*
 489 *but finite* distribution of β_{eff} at the chosen calibration ra-
 490 dius. Table 2 shows that β_{eff} spans a non-zero interval
 491 across the disk sample (i.e. the ridge has structured scat-
 492 ter rather than exact constancy), and the fitted normal-
 493 ization is therefore an empirical *benchmark band* rather
 494 than a fundamental constant. The empirical content
 495 thus lies in: (i) *radial coherence* of $G_{\text{rot}}(r_i)$ within in-
 496 dividual systems when multiple tuples are available, (ii)
 497 the *finite width* and internal structure of the ridge across
 498 the disk sample, and (iii) *cross-channel behavior* when
 499 additional tracers and characteristic radii are included.

500 *Pressure-supported dwarfs as a distinct channel.*—

501 Pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ map into
 502 the same tuple plane via the same inversion (Eq. (11);
 503 equivalently Eq. (10)), but the resulting β_{eff} values can
 504 show systematic regime-dependent behavior with g_N .
 505 This is consistent with the fact that the (g_N, g_{obs}) pro-
 506 jection can become multi-valued in the resolved dwarf
 507 regime (Júlio et al. 2025). The inferred dwarf response
 508 fractions cluster closer to unity (median $\beta_{\text{eff}} \simeq 0.99$ in
 509 Table 3) than the disk tuples (median $\beta_{\text{eff}} \simeq 0.83$ in Ta-
 510 ble 2), even when the tuple-plane ridge residuals remain

small. The tuple-plane representation does not require strict universality across dynamical states; instead, it makes regime-dependent deviations directly measurable and testable.

Weak-lensing anchor.—Weak-lensing reconstructions extend the RAR into the low-acceleration halo regime by ~ 2.5 dex beyond the direct reach of rotation curves (Mistele et al. 2024). This provides an independent low-acceleration mass channel and motivates explicit cross-channel consistency tests of the tuple-plane ridge structure on $\gtrsim 100\text{--}300$ kpc scales.

5.2. Relation to RAR/MOND-style descriptions

At the level of radial equilibrium, the response identity

$$g_{\text{obs}}(r) = \frac{g_N(r)}{1 - \beta_{\text{eff}}(r)}$$

is algebraically equivalent to a ν -law $g_{\text{obs}} = \nu g_N$ with $\nu = (1 - \beta_{\text{eff}})^{-1}$. For rotation-supported disks, an illustrative mapping $\beta_{\text{eff}}(g_N)$ reproduces the standard McGaugh RAR representation (Sect. 4.1).

RAR as a projection versus tuple-plane constraints.—A universal RAR posits a single-valued mapping $g_{\text{obs}} = f(g_N)$ in the two-dimensional (g_N, g_{obs}) plane. By contrast, the present framework is defined by radius-local inversion of Eq. (10) (equivalently Eq. (11)), mapping co-located tuples $(M(< r), r, v(r))$ into the (M, G_{rot}) tuple plane. The empirical content therefore lies not only in the existence of a trend but in additional coherence requirements: (i) $G_{\text{rot}}(r)$ should be approximately radius-coherent within a system when multiple tuples are available, (ii) independent tracers and characteristic radii should populate a consistent ridge band in the tuple plane, and (iii) the tuple-plane organization can remain informative even when the (g_N, g_{obs}) projection becomes multi-valued.

Only if the RAR were strictly universal, single-valued, and radius-independent would the tuple-plane ridge reduce to a trivial rewriting. The evidence considered here motivates treating “RAR universality” as a falsifiable hypothesis rather than an assumed property across all dynamical states.

Dimensional structure.—Mathematically, the RAR is a two-dimensional functional relation $g_{\text{obs}} = f(g_N)$ in the acceleration plane. The G_{rot} framework evaluates a radius-local inversion in the three-dimensional tuple space $(M(< r), r, v(r))$ and tests coherence in the derived (M, G_{rot}) plane. The additional empirical information content therefore resides in coherence and cross-channel stability constraints that are not fixed by the RAR projection alone.

5.3. Interpretation space: what is not fixed by the data

The G_{rot} ridge is presented as an empirical compression of galaxy-scale phenomenology and does not, by itself, select a unique microscopic mechanism. Several broad interpretations are compatible with the current evidence and can be distinguished only through additional, independent constraints:

- **Halo response / baryon–halo coupling (GR+DM).** Eq. (10) can be read as an effective dynamical mass mapping $M_{\text{dyn}} = M_{\text{bar}}/(1 - \beta_{\text{eff}})$, where the observed β_{eff} distribution reflects correlations between baryonic structure, assembly history, and halo structure. In this interpretation, the ridge width and regime dependence are expected to encode physically meaningful variation (e.g. surface density, feedback efficiency, environment).
- **Modified-dynamics ν -law (without explicit halo).** Alternatively, $\nu = (1 - \beta_{\text{eff}})^{-1}$ can be interpreted as an effective modification of the dynamical relation between g_N and g_{obs} in the weak-field regime. In this reading, G_{rot} is an empirical coefficient whose microphysical origin is left open and constrained by lensing–dynamics consistency.
- **Emergent structural self-similarity (conservative interpretation).** A non-microscopic interpretation is that the narrow but finite distribution of $M_{\text{ref}}G_{\text{rot}}$ in the rotation-supported regime reflects emergent self-organization of extended disks in approximate virial equilibrium with characteristic structural scaling. In this view, the ridge is an empirical regularity of galaxy formation and equilibrium structure rather than a fundamental symmetry; the observed ridge width and regime dependence are then natural diagnostics rather than anomalies.

Relation to MOND-based classification schemes.—Recent work has proposed classification frameworks based explicitly on MOND-inspired indices and timescale criteria (Eappen & Kroupa 2026). These approaches embed the classification in a specific modified-gravity paradigm (via a_0 and MOND depth measures), whereas the present tuple-plane framework remains theory-agnostic and is defined by radius-local inversion of observed tuples. Both approaches emphasize regime dependence, but they differ in mathematical structure and in the role of assumed fundamental scales.

Related work on distinct RAR behavior across environments.—Distinct RAR behavior across gravitational environ-

ments (e.g. galaxies versus clusters) has also been discussed in alternative-gravity contexts (Monjo & Banik 2025). Such results motivate extending tuple-plane tests to additional environments (e.g. clusters) as a stringent falsification opportunity.

No implied upper mass bound.—The consistency condition $1 - M(< r)G_{\text{rot}}/(4\pi^2) > 0$ does not imply an upper limit on galaxy mass. Under the empirical scaling $G_{\text{rot}} = K_{\text{rot}}/M_{\text{ref}}$, the product MG_{rot} follows a narrow, but not strictly constant, distribution across the rotation-supported calibration domain; the bound therefore constrains the allowed normalization range rather than the absolute baryonic mass.

5.4. Limitations and systematics

The framework is empirical and radius-local. Several systematics can affect the inferred coefficients and the ridge width: (i) uncertainties in baryonic masses $M(< r)$ (mass-to-light ratios, gas corrections, distances), (ii) tracer interpretation and modeling assumptions (e.g. anisotropy in pressure-supported systems), and (iii) departures from steady state (tides, mergers, transient features). These effects can produce structured scatter and channel-dependent offsets; they are therefore part of the falsifiable content rather than mere nuisances.

5.5. Falsifiable targets and next steps

Quantitative falsification criteria.—The tuple-plane organization is empirically falsified if any of the following hold: (i) the fitted slope of the $G_{\text{rot}}-M$ relation deviates significantly from -1 across independent samples, (ii) the ridge width (e.g. the variance of $M_{\text{ref}}G_{\text{rot}}$ or, equivalently, of Δ_{ridge} as quantified in the calibration section) grows systematically with mass, radius, or tracer, (iii) radial coherence fails within individual rotation-supported systems when multiple tuples are available, or (iv) independent dynamical environments (e.g. clusters) exhibit statistically significant normalization shifts inconsistent with a structured but continuous extension of the disk scaling. Importantly, exact constancy of β_{eff} is not required; the hypothesis concerns the existence of a narrow, structured scaling relation whose regime-dependent deviations remain internally coherent and reproducible across independent data products.

Order parameter versus effective acceleration.—If G_{rot} is interpreted as an empirical order parameter, then the additional term

$$a_{\text{rot}} = g_{\text{obs}} - g_N$$

should not be regarded as a separately specified microscopic force law, but as the observable dynamical con-

sequence of an ordered weak-field regime. In this view, G_{rot} is diagnostic rather than causal: it measures the degree to which a system occupies this organized dynamical state, but does not by itself generate the additional acceleration. Equivalently, a_{rot} characterizes the effective departure from the baryonic Newtonian expectation, while G_{rot} provides a compact empirical measure of how this departure is organized across systems and radii.

Outlook: structural correlates of the ridge.—If G_{rot} indeed acts as an empirical order parameter, then the residuals about the tuple-plane ridge should correlate not only with enclosed baryonic mass, but also with structural or dynamical indicators. Particularly informative candidates are rotational coherence, v/σ , mean surface density, specific angular momentum, and environmental or merger-history diagnostics. One possible, explicitly non-unique physical reading is that these quantities trace the degree of ordering of the underlying dynamical state, with G_{rot} representing the tuple-plane projection of that ordering rather than a separate microscopic force law.

Detecting such correlations would provide a direct clue to the physical origin of the observed ordering and help distinguish between halo-response interpretations, modified-dynamics descriptions, and emergent self-organization scenarios.

6. CONCLUSIONS

An empirical response framework has been formulated to organize late-time weak-field galaxy dynamics across rotation-supported systems and pressure-supported dwarfs. The approach is based on radius-local inversion of co-located tuples $(M(< r), r, v(r))$, yielding an empirical response coefficient G_{rot} that can be compared across systems and dynamical regimes without committing to a specific microscopic interpretation.

In the rotation-supported calibration domain, the inferred coefficients populate a tight inverse-mass ridge over approximately five decades in enclosed baryonic mass, including an independent halo-scale galaxy-galaxy lensing and satellite-kinematics cross-check at $r \simeq 200$ kpc. The ridge exhibits finite but structured scatter rather than exact constancy, corresponding to a narrow distribution of the response fraction β_{eff} rather than a universal invariant. The empirical content therefore lies in the stability of the ridge structure, its finite width, and the coherence of inferred coefficients when evaluated at different characteristic radii and with different tracers.

Extending the same tuple-plane diagnostic to pressure-supported dwarfs evaluated at $r_{1/2}$ increases

707 the dynamic range to more than eight decades in en-
708 closed baryonic mass. In the tuple plane, the dwarf
709 channel remains consistent with the inverse-mass ridge
710 within the quoted uncertainties, while exhibiting a sys-
711 tematically higher response fraction (i.e., β_{eff} closer to
712 unity) than the disk calibration tuples. This behavior is
713 compatible with the broadened and potentially multi-
714 valued loci reported for pressure-supported dwarfs in
715 the resolved (g_N, g_{obs}) plane, and it motivates explicit
716 state-conditioning tests rather than enforcing a univer-
717 sal single-valued RAR projection across all dynamical

718 regimes.

719 The formulation is explicitly empirical and defines
720 quantitative falsification targets based on slope stability,
721 normalization drift, ridge width, radial coherence within
722 individual systems, and cross-channel consistency. Fu-
723 ture work can extend these tests to additional environ-
724 ments (e.g. galaxy clusters) and incorporate improved
725 baryonic mass modeling and tracer systematics to fur-
726 ther constrain the origin of the observed tuple-plane
727 structure.

APPENDIX

A. TABLE II GALAXY DATA

Table 2. Tuple-based inference of G_{rot} for the disk calibration sample.

Galaxy	G_{rot} (kg^{-1})	M_{ref} (kg)	v (m s^{-1})	r (kpc)	β_{eff}	References
Milky Way	2.20×10^{-40}	1.49×10^{41}	2.28×10^5	36.5	0.83	Bland-Hawthorn & Gerhard (2016); Sofue (2016)
M31	1.25×10^{-40}	2.38×10^{41}	2.43×10^5	35.0	0.75	Tamm et al. (2012); Sofue (2015)
Cartwheel	1.07×10^{-40}	2.77×10^{41}	2.19×10^5	50.0	0.75	Higdon et al. (2015); Amram et al. (1998)
NGC 6503	3.06×10^{-39}	1.17×10^{40}	1.17×10^5	20.0	0.91	Greisen et al. (2009); Bottema & Gerritsen (1997)
NGC 4631	3.10×10^{-40}	8.14×10^{40}	1.72×10^5	16.5	0.64	Irwin et al. (2011); Sofue et al. (1999)
NGC 3992	1.35×10^{-40}	2.18×10^{41}	2.49×10^5	30.0	0.75	Bottema (2002)
NGC 3198	7.52×10^{-40}	4.36×10^{40}	1.59×10^5	22.0	0.83	Gentile et al. (2013); Karukes et al. (2015); Sofue et al. (1999)
NGC 2841	1.39×10^{-40}	2.18×10^{41}	2.85×10^5	25.0	0.77	Samurović (2015)
NGC 1097	1.51×10^{-40}	1.84×10^{41}	2.53×10^5	21.0	0.70	Lin et al. (2013); Sofue et al. (1999)
NGC 5055	1.92×10^{-40}	1.49×10^{41}	1.97×10^5	30.0	0.72	Battaglia et al. (2006); Sofue et al. (1999)
NGC 660	5.79×10^{-40}	5.25×10^{40}	1.57×10^5	20.0	0.77	van Driel et al. (1995); Sofue et al. (1999)
NGC 300	4.05×10^{-39}	7.93×10^{39}	9.60×10^4	10.0	0.81	Puche & Carignan (1990); Westmeier et al. (2011)
NGC 6946	1.94×10^{-40}	1.37×10^{41}	2.24×10^5	18.0	0.67	de Blok et al. (2008); Oman et al. (2016)
LSB F64	4.15×10^{-37}	8.66×10^{37}	3.30×10^4	1.9	0.91	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 7793	3.81×10^{-39}	7.89×10^{39}	1.14×10^5	5.5	0.76	de Blok et al. (2008); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 52	4.71×10^{-38}	7.63×10^{38}	6.05×10^4	5.0	0.91	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 5204	3.30×10^{-38}	1.06×10^{39}	9.00×10^4	2.5	0.89	Adams et al. (2014); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 2403	2.00×10^{-39}	1.73×10^{40}	1.40×10^5	16.0	0.88	de Blok et al. (2008); Oman et al. (2016); Sofue et al. (1999)
UGC 11707	5.45×10^{-39}	6.34×10^{39}	1.05×10^5	10.0	0.88	Adams et al. (2014); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 126	9.31×10^{-38}	3.53×10^{38}	3.90×10^4	3.0	0.83	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 70	3.23×10^{-37}	1.14×10^{38}	4.30×10^4	2.0	0.93	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
UGC 8508	9.85×10^{-37}	3.92×10^{37}	4.50×10^4	1.9	0.98	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 87	5.79×10^{-38}	6.34×10^{38}	5.30×10^4	7.0	0.93	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 2552	7.73×10^{-39}	4.30×10^{39}	9.50×10^4	6.5	0.84	Adams et al. (2014); Oman et al. (2016)
IC 2574	5.85×10^{-39}	5.63×10^{39}	7.82×10^4	12.0	0.83	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 154	5.01×10^{-38}	7.20×10^{38}	4.90×10^4	7.5	0.91	Oh et al. (2015); de Blok et al. (2008)

Table 2 continued

Table 2 (*continued*)

Galaxy	G_{rot} (kg^{-1})	M_{ref} (kg)	v (m s^{-1})	r (kpc)	β_{eff}	References
DDO 50	7.71×10^{-39}	2.83×10^{39}	3.70×10^4	10.0	0.55	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
IC 1613	1.42×10^{-37}	1.74×10^{38}	2.00×10^4	2.5	0.62	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 1569	2.12×10^{-38}	1.12×10^{39}	4.50×10^4	3.0	0.60	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 43	6.91×10^{-38}	4.64×10^{38}	3.80×10^4	3.7	0.81	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 2366	1.43×10^{-38}	2.26×10^{39}	5.80×10^4	8.0	0.82	Oh et al. (2015); de Blok et al. (2008)
DDO 47	3.98×10^{-38}	9.28×10^{38}	6.50×10^4	7.5	0.94	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
DDO 168	5.86×10^{-38}	6.26×10^{38}	6.00×10^4	5.3	0.93	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
NGC 3621	6.21×10^{-40}	5.11×10^{40}	1.50×10^5	25.0	0.80	de Blok et al. (2008); Oman et al. (2016)
Haro 29	1.67×10^{-37}	2.14×10^{38}	3.30×10^4	4.5	0.91	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)
WLM	1.85×10^{-37}	1.90×10^{38}	3.70×10^4	2.7	0.89	Oh et al. (2015); Oman et al. (2016)

NOTE—For each rotation-supported galaxy (including gas-rich dwarfs), the table lists the co-located tuple ($M_{\text{ref}}, r_{\text{ref}}, v(r_{\text{ref}})$) with $M_{\text{ref}} \equiv M(< r_{\text{ref}})$, together with G_{rot} inferred from Eq. (10) and $\beta_{\text{eff}} = M_{\text{ref}}G_{\text{rot}}/(4\pi^2)$. Pressure-supported dwarfs are evaluated separately at $r_{1/2}$ in Table 3.

B. TABLE III: PRESSURE-SUPPORTED DWARFS (JÚLIO ET AL.) AT $R_{1/2}$ **Table 3.** Pressure-supported dwarf sample (Júlio et al. 2025) evaluated at the half-light radius $r_{1/2}$.

Galaxy	$M_{\text{tot}} (M_{\odot})$	$M_{\text{bar}} (M_{\odot})$	$r_{1/2}$ (kpc)	$v_c(r_{1/2})$ (m s $^{-1}$)	$g_{\text{obs}}(r_{1/2})$ (m s $^{-2}$)	$g_N(r_{1/2})$ (m s $^{-2}$)	β_{eff}	G_{rot} (kg $^{-1}$)
Carina	$6.11 \times 10^{6+1.6 \times 10^6}_{-2.8 \times 10^6}$	1.75×10^5	2.48×10^{-1}	1.02×10^4	1.37×10^{-11}	3.93×10^{-13}	9.71×10^{-1}	1.10×10^{-34}
Draco	$9.87 \times 10^{6+5.3 \times 10^5}_{-1.9 \times 10^6}$	1.09×10^5	2.23×10^{-1}	1.38×10^4	2.75×10^{-11}	3.04×10^{-13}	9.89×10^{-1}	1.81×10^{-34}
Leo I	$8.75 \times 10^{6+9.3 \times 10^7}_{-2.8 \times 10^6}$	1.25×10^6	2.52×10^{-1}	1.22×10^4	1.91×10^{-11}	2.73×10^{-12}	8.57×10^{-1}	1.36×10^{-35}
Leo II	$6.60 \times 10^{6+1.6 \times 10^6}_{-1.9 \times 10^6}$	3.29×10^5	1.76×10^{-1}	1.27×10^4	2.95×10^{-11}	1.47×10^{-12}	9.50×10^{-1}	5.73×10^{-35}
Sculptor	$1.05 \times 10^{7+3.1 \times 10^6}_{-2.0 \times 10^6}$	1.01×10^6	2.82×10^{-1}	1.26×10^4	1.83×10^{-11}	1.76×10^{-12}	9.04×10^{-1}	1.78×10^{-35}
Sextans	$5.74 \times 10^{7+1.2 \times 10^7}_{-1.3 \times 10^7}$	4.63×10^5	6.92×10^{-1}	1.88×10^4	1.66×10^{-11}	1.34×10^{-13}	9.92×10^{-1}	4.25×10^{-35}
Ursa minor	$5.51 \times 10^{6+2.8 \times 10^6}_{-4.2 \times 10^6}$	6.20×10^4	1.83×10^{-1}	1.13×10^4	2.28×10^{-11}	2.57×10^{-13}	9.89×10^{-1}	3.17×10^{-34}
Antlia B	$1.09 \times 10^{7+2.1 \times 10^7}_{-4.0 \times 10^6}$	4.65×10^5	2.72×10^{-1}	1.31×10^4	2.03×10^{-11}	8.68×10^{-13}	9.57×10^{-1}	4.08×10^{-35}
Eridanus II	$9.73 \times 10^{6+6.3 \times 10^6}_{-4.1 \times 10^6}$	5.47×10^4	2.74×10^{-1}	1.23×10^4	1.79×10^{-11}	1.01×10^{-13}	9.94×10^{-1}	3.61×10^{-34}
Grus 1	$3.55 \times 10^{6+3.2 \times 10^6}_{-2.6 \times 10^6}$	5.24×10^3	1.51×10^{-1}	9.99×10^3	2.14×10^{-11}	3.16×10^{-14}	9.99×10^{-1}	3.78×10^{-33}
Leo T	$4.07 \times 10^{6+3.0 \times 10^6}_{-3.1 \times 10^6}$	4.55×10^4	1.14×10^{-1}	1.23×10^4	4.33×10^{-11}	4.84×10^{-13}	9.89×10^{-1}	4.31×10^{-34}

NOTE— The table lists the reported dynamical total masses M_{tot} (including quoted asymmetric uncertainty bounds) and baryonic masses $M_{\text{bar}} (< r_{1/2})$, as well as kinematic accelerations and radii. The equivalent circular-speed proxy $v_c(r_{1/2}) \equiv \sqrt{g_{\text{obs}}(r_{1/2}) r_{1/2}}$ is provided to construct the co-located tuple at the measurement radius. The response coefficient G_{rot} is inferred by applying the tuple inversion (Eq. (11); equivalently Eq. (10)) at $r_{1/2}$. Values are digitized from Appendix C (GravSphere fits) of Júlio et al. (2025). Fornax is omitted because Júlio et al. (2025) discuss it as a physically distinct outlier (higher mass and extended star-formation history, with possible core formation) and it is treated separately as a sensitivity check.

REFERENCES

- 731 Adams, J. J., Simon, J. D., Fabricius, M. H., et al. 2014,
732 ApJ, 789, 63, doi: [10.1088/0004-637X/789/1/63](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/789/1/63)
- 733 Amram, P., Mendes de Oliveira, C., Boulesteix, J., &
734 Balkowski, C. 1998, A&A, 330, 881, doi: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1998A&A...330..881A>
- 735 Battaglia, G., Fraternali, F., Oosterloo, T., & Sancisi, R.
736 2006, A&A, 447, 49, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/20053210](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/20053210)
- 737 Bland-Hawthorn, J., & Gerhard, O. 2016, ARA&A, 54,
738 529, doi: [10.1146/annurev-astro-081915-023441](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-081915-023441)
- 739 Bogdán, Á., & Vogelsberger, M. 2022, arXiv e-prints,
740 doi: [10.48550/arXiv.2206.11906](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.11906)
- 741 Bois, M., Emsellem, E., Bournaud, F., et al. 2011, MNRAS,
742 416, 1654, doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19113.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19113.x)
- 743 Bottema, R. 2002, A&A, 388, 793,
744 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/20020539](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/20020539)
- 745 Bottema, R., & Gerritsen, J. P. E. 1997, MNRAS, 290, 585,
746 doi: [10.1093/mnras/290.4.585](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/290.4.585)
- 747 Bregman, J. N., Anderson, M. E., Miller, M. J., et al. 2018,
748 ApJ, 862, 3, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/aacafe](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aacafe)
- 749 Cappellari, M. 2008, MNRAS, 390, 71,
750 doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13754.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13754.x)
- 751 Cappellari, M., Emsellem, E., Bacon, R., et al. 2007,
752 MNRAS, 379, 418, doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11963.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11963.x)
- 753 Comparat, J., Truong, N., Merloni, A., et al. 2022, A&A,
754 666, A156, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202243101](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202243101)
- 755 de Blok, W. J. G., Walter, F., Brinks, E., et al. 2008, AJ,
756 136, 2648, doi: [10.1088/0004-6256/136/6/2648](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/136/6/2648)
- 757 Dey, A., Schlegel, D. J., Lang, D., et al. 2019, AJ, 157, 168,
758 doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab089d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab089d)
- 759 Duc, P., Cuillandre, J., Serra, P., et al. 2011, MNRAS, 417,
760 863, doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19137.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19137.x)
- 761 Eappen, R., & Kroupa, P. 2026, Galaxies, 14,
762 doi: [10.3390/galaxies14020022](https://doi.org/10.3390/galaxies14020022)
- 763 Emsellem, E., Cappellari, M., Krajnović, D., et al. 2011,
764 MNRAS, 414, 888, doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18496.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18496.x)
- 765 Gentile, G., et al. 2013, A&A, 554, A125,
766 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201321116](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201321116)
- 767 Greisen, E. W., Spekkens, K., & van Moorsel, G. A. 2009,
768 AJ, 137, 4718, doi: [10.1088/0004-6256/137/6/4718](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/137/6/4718)
- 769 Higdon, J. L., Higdon, S. J. U., Martín Ruiz, S., & Rand,
770 R. J. 2015, ApJL, 814, L1,
771 doi: [10.1088/2041-8205/814/1/L1](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/814/1/L1)

- 773 Irwin, J. A., Wilson, C. D., Wiegert, T., et al. 2011,
774 MNRAS, 410, 1423,
775 doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17510.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17510.x)
- 776 Júlio, M. P., Read, J. I., Pawlowski, M. S., et al. 2025,
777 A&A, 704, A330, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202557106](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202557106)
- 778 Karukes, E. V., Salucci, P., & Gentile, G. 2015, A&A, 578,
779 A13, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201425339](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201425339)
- 780 Koopmans, L. V. E., Auger, M., Barnabè, M., et al. 2009,
781 doi: [10.48550/arXiv.0902.3186](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.0902.3186)
- 782 Krajnović, D., Emsellem, E., Cappellari, M., et al. 2020,
783 A&A, 635, A129, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201937040](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201937040)
- 784 Kroupa, P. 2012, PASA, 29, 395, doi: [10.1071/AS12005](https://doi.org/10.1071/AS12005)
- 785 Lin, L.-H., Wang, H.-H., Hsieh, P.-Y., et al. 2013, ApJ, 771,
786 8, doi: [10.1088/0004-637X/771/1/8](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/771/1/8)
- 787 Ma, L., Zhang, Z., Wang, H., & Wu, X. 2025, ApJ, 984,
788 101, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/adc728](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/adc728)
- 789 McGaugh, S. S., Lelli, F., & Schombert, J. M. 2016, Phys.
790 Rev. Lett., 117, 201101,
791 doi: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.201101](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.201101)
- 792 Meurer, G. R., Zheng, Z., Thilker, D., et al. 2018, MNRAS,
793 476, 1624, doi: [10.1093/mnras/sty275](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty275)
- 794 Milgrom, M. 1983, ApJ, 270, 365, doi: [10.1086/161130](https://doi.org/10.1086/161130)
- 795 Mistele, T., McGaugh, S., Lelli, F., Schombert, J., & Li, P.
796 2024, JCAP, 04, 20, doi: [10.1088/1475-7516/2024/04/020](https://doi.org/10.1088/1475-7516/2024/04/020)
- 797 Monjo, R., & Banik, I. 2025, ApJ, 992, 35,
798 doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/adfcc0](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/adfcc0)
- 799 Moody, R. J., Romanowsky, A. J., Cox, T. J., et al. 2014,
800 MNRAS, 444, 1475, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stu1444](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu1444)
- 801 Naab, T., Jesseit, R., & Burkert, A. 2006, MNRAS, 372,
802 839, doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10902.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10902.x)
- 803 Nicastro, F., Kaastra, J., Krongold, Y., et al. 2023, ApJL,
804 955, L21, doi: [10.3847/2041-8213/acec70](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/acec70)
- 805 Oh, S.-H., Hunter, D. A., Brinks, E., et al. 2015, AJ, 149,
806 180, doi: [10.1088/0004-6256/149/6/180](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/149/6/180)
- 807 Oman, K. A., Navarro, J. F., Sales, L. V., et al. 2016,
808 MNRAS, 460, 3610, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stw1251](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw1251)
- 809 Ou, X., Necib, L., Wetzel, A., et al. 2025, ApJ, 994, 128,
810 doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ae0b63](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ae0b63)
- 811 Puche, D., & Carignan, C. 1990, AJ, 100, 1468,
812 doi: [10.1086/115612](https://doi.org/10.1086/115612)
- 813 Samurović, S. 2015, MNRAS, 451, 4073,
814 doi: [10.1093/mnras/stv1226](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv1226)
- 815 Sofue, Y. 2015, PASJ, 67, 75, doi: [10.1093/pasj/psv042](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/psv042)
- 816 —. 2016, PASJ, 69, R1, doi: [10.1093/pasj/psw103](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/psw103)
- 817 Sofue, Y., Tutui, Y., Honma, M., et al. 1999, ApJ, 523, 136,
818 doi: [10.1086/307731](https://doi.org/10.1086/307731)
- 819 Sonnenfeld, A., Tortora, C., Hoekstra, H., et al. 2022,
820 A&A, 662, A55, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202142511](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202142511)
- 821 Tamm, A., Tempel, E., Tenjes, P., Tihhonova, O., &
822 Tuvikene, T. 2012, A&A, 546, A4,
823 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201220065](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201220065)
- 824 van Driel, W., Combes, F., Casoli, F., et al. 1995, AJ, 109,
825 942, doi: [10.1086/117333](https://doi.org/10.1086/117333)
- 826 Westmeier, T., Braun, R., & Koribalski, B. S. 2011,
827 MNRAS, 410, 2217,
828 doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17596.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17596.x)
- 829 Zhang, Z., Wang, H., Luo, W., et al. 2022, A&A, 663, A16,
830 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202142866](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202142866)